

Cara

also known as "Caranquí Confederation", "Kingdom of Quito"

By Ryan Hechler, Tulane University

Entry tags: Religious Group, Unclassified Barbaocoan, Barbaocoan, Language, Indigenous Theology, Indigenous tribal

The Cara were a Barbaocoan ethnic group that lived in the northern highlands of modern Ecuador and were defined by a series of chiefdoms with their own semi-autonomous power. While the majority of local populations lived dispersed and within rural contexts, chiefly power was spiritually expressed at monumental centers. Major centers of power were Caranqui, Cayambe, Cochasquí, Otavalo, and Quinche. The role of chiefs appears to have served both political and religious functions. Collectively, the Cara had more than 60 ritual monumental centers which collectively had more than 200 massive earthen platform mounds, known locally as tolas. Many of these tolas had entry ramps as long as 300 m which led to circular temple structures on the summits. Many of these ramps terminated at important water features, such as rivers and quebradas. During the Inka Empire's conquest of the Cara in the 15th century, the region became generally known as the Kingdom of Quito.

Date Range: 950 CE - 1532 CE

Region: Cara

Region tags: Ecuador, Imbabura, Pichincha, Andes, South America

The extent of Cara religious monumental centers and settlements at the point of Spanish Conquest.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Athens, J. Stephen. "Ethnicity and Adaptation: The Late Period-Cara Occupation in Northern Highland Ecuador." In *Resources, Power, and Interregional Interaction*, edited by Edward Schortman and Patricia Urban, 193-219. New York: Plenum Press, 1992.
- Source 2: Echeverría Almeida, José. *Las sociedades prehispánicas de la Sierra Norte del Ecuador: una aproximación arqueológica y antropológica*. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, 2004.
- Source 3: Oberem, Udo, and Wolfgang Wurster. *Excavaciones en Cochasquí, Ecuador, 1964-1965*. Mainz Am Rhein: Verlag Philipp von Zabern, 1989.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://repositorio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/handle/10469/5745>
- Source 1 Description: Athens, J. Stephen. *Etnicidad y adaptación: El Periodo Tardío de la ocupación Cara en la Sierra Norte del Ecuador*. Sarance, Vol. 24, pp. 161-204, 1997.
- Source 2 URL: <https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/9877-opac>
- Source 2 Description: Salomon, Frank. *Los señores étnicos de Quito en la época de los Incas*. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, 1980.
- Source 3 URL: https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/abya_yala/244/
- Source 3 Description: Caillavet, Chantal. *Etnias del norte: Etnohistoria e historia de Ecuador*. Quito: Ediciones Abya-Yala, 2000.
- Notes: <https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/143177-opac> Espinoza Soriano, Waldemar. *Los Cayambes y Carangues: Siglos XV-XVI, El Testimonio de la Etnohistoria*. 3 vols. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, 1988.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/cieza-de-leon-pedro-de.-cronica-del-peru.-el-senorio-de-los-incas-2005>
- Source 1 Description: Cieza de León, Pedro de. *Crónica del Perú: El Señorío de los Incas*, edited by Franklin Pease G.Y. Caracas: Biblioteca Ayacucho, [1553] 2005. An important source for understanding the region.
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/miscelanea-antartica>
- Source 2 Description: Cabello Balboa, Miguel. *Miscelánea antártica: una historia del Perú antiguo*. Lima: Instituto de Etnología y Arqueología, Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos, [1586] 1951.
- Source 3 URL: <https://archive.org/details/betanzos-juan-de.-suma-y-narracion-de-los-incas-1880>
- Source 3 Description: Diez de Betanzos, Juan. *Suma y narración de los Incas*, edited by Marcos Jiménez de la Espada. Madrid: Imprenta de Manuel G. Hernández, [died 1576] 1880.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Yes

Notes: Tawantinsuyu (the Inka Empire) partially incorporated the Cara under Emperor Thupa Inka Yupanki in the mid-15th century. The relationship appears to have been more of an acquiescence to imperial pressures - a mixture of fortifications and Inka settlements, the latter of which was amongst local populations and independent of them, as well as economic courting via prestige goods. The Inka also embedded themselves amongst religious centers of the Cara and established ushnus (ritual stone platform structures meant for veneration of Inti, the Inka sun god) in settlement and military contexts. After Thupa Inka Yupanki's death, the succession of his son Wayna Qhapaq brought the largest rebellion in the history of Tawantinsuyu with the Cara leading a multi-year regional revolt. Various Spanish colonial-era chroniclers have suggested this was a result of religious, political, and economic disagreements. The Inka brutally subdued the rebellion with a massacre of adult Cara men at a lake near Caranquí, which was subsequently named in Quechua (the language of the Inka) Yawarqucha, or "Blood Lake." Acts of spiritual incorporation and disrespect can be seen from the Inka occupation. At Cochaski, the largest platform mound (tola) of the site was in the process of being ritually coopted by the Inka with Inka-style blocks adorning the pyramid. Important imperial Inka ceramics have been found on many platform mounds of the Cara, particularly ritual vessels such as the aribalo which was often used for chicha (corn beer) libations. At Quinche, the whole population was deported and mitmaqkuna (conquered ethnic groups from elsewhere within the empire) were relocated here. Many Cara populations next to major religious ritual centers were deported to other Inka settlements in modern Ecuador, Peru, and Bolivia.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— Yes

Notes: Ethnic affiliation appears to have equated to religious affiliation. Elites controlled access to monumental spaces that housed temple structures (Jijón y Caamaño 1914: 295-298; Gondard & López 1983: 267; Oberem & Wurster 1989).

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

— Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

— No

↳ Assigned by class:

— Yes

Notes: Religious participation within temple structures was likely limited to elites and their families.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by gender:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

— Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear if the spread of the Cara religious centers equated to territorial expansion of the group itself or the adoption of monumental practices by culturally similar neighboring groups. An area that has given researchers trouble is the southernly extension directly east of modern Quito (Jijón y Caamaño 1914: 300; 1951: 75; Athens 1992: 198-199; 1997: 167).

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Religious infrastructure is a labor investment by collective members of the polity. Thus while this is not paid in a currency transactional sense, it is a collective endeavor that is likely entrenched in some notion of community reciprocity. The labor investment is exponential for the creation of monumental centers and relies on general members of the polity (Osborn & Athens 1974).

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 155000

Notes: The Cara were subjected to the political and ritual power of their respective chiefs, thus technically the whole population would be expected to fall under the religio-cultural belief system. At the time of Inka Conquest, it has been estimated that the population was between 110,000 and 200,000, with 155,000 being the agreed upon estimate by Knapp (1984: 339).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 100

Notes: Religious and ethnic affiliation appear to be the same.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The Cara did not have a written language. Unfortunately, many oral mythistory did not survive the sequential conquests of the Inka Empire and the Spanish Empire. Much of the more outlandish stories of the Cara were written by Juan de Velasco ([1789] 1841-44), more than two centuries after Spanish conquest. Much of Velasco's accounts are problematic and need to be viewed critically (Willingham 2014), although there are occasional points that may have grains of truth. It should be noted that one of his principal sources was an Indigenous writer named Jacinto Collahuaso.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The term tola is used to describe various earthen monumental structures. From around 950 CE to 1280 CE, large round burial mounds were built for a central elite figure (male or female). A central, tiered shaft tomb was created to honor this elite figure who was interred with local and foreign goods (from a mixture of the highlands and the Amazon). There is some evidence of sacrifice, with skulls sometimes surrounding the central burial. There is also evidence of these mortuary mounds being created without an actual interment, possibly out of respect for someone who could not be formally buried (e.g., a result of death abroad). Around 1280 CE the region was blanketed in ~10 cm of ashfall from the Quilotoa Eruption which had a Volcanic Explosivity Index of 6 (larger than the infamous Pompeii Eruption). This was one of several major volcanic events during the climatic shift to the Little Ice Age. Perhaps related to this, around this time we see the introduction of monumental platform mounds often with circular temple structures on their summit. The platform mounds themselves may be inspired by the highly volcanic landscape of the region. Many had different stages of development and were gradually expanded upon throughout time. Thus far, there is limited evidence of sacrifice being practiced during this period. The largest platform mound at Cochasquí was coopted by the Inka and more than 500 skulls were found within a corridor that bifurcated the mounds summit. The corridor was adorned with Inka blocks and, unfortunately due to preservation issues and large-scale looting of the human remains, it is unclear if this could be indicative of the local rebellion against the Inka or the subsequent Inka reconquest of the religious center, which was burned. For both the Cara and the Inka, such an interment is very atypical and seems to be a result of military action. Many of these platform mounds had large entry ramps for ritual procession, being as long as 300 m. Some of

these ramps intentionally terminate at prominent water features, such as quebradas of volcanoes or local rivers.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Monumental sites appear to have been isolated from formal villages. The Cara lived in dispersed, rural homesteads and would congregate at their nearby monumental centers for ritual events.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Cara settlement studies are virtually nonexistent, part of this can be attributed to the rural nature of homesteads and part of this can also be attributed to the nature of Spanish colonial village development, which likely subsumed more concentrated areas. With this in mind, the largest monumental site is that of Zuleta and the pyramids and mounds dominate a valley.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Elite monumental tombs were established with large round burial mounds. These monumental endeavors defined the region between 950 CE to about 1280 CE. Offerings of ceramics (local and from the Amazon) and human skulls have been documented within this. Subsequent mortuary contexts (1280 CE to Spanish Conquest) have been more modest, with commoners being found in a flexed position on their side in shallow shaft tombs without noticeable markers on the landscape with grave goods ranging from nothing to several ceramics. It is common to find random burials amongst monumental centers and thus far no clear planning has been identified for this. There has not been a burial that has been identified from this later period that is clearly elite, although the sample size is admittedly limited.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: There are clear, planned cemetery areas of elites via large round burial mounds from about 950 CE to 1280 CE. These burial mounds are often placed around important natural landscape elements, such as prominent rivers and quebradas. Later period burials appear to be more sporadic.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Circular temples are present on the summits of platform mounds. Platform mounds can have one or two temple structures on their summit. There is some variability. These are thought of as developing between approximately 1280 CE to Spanish Conquest.

↳ Altars:

– No

Notes: While there are clear temple spaces, the presence of actual altars within these has not been suggested archaeologically.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

Notes: While there are not specific devotional markers that indicate the Cara religion, a common artifact found at religious centers are abstract, clay anthropomorphic figurines that often appear to be intentionally broken.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Summits of earthen platform mounds likely served as gathering spaces for the privileged few that could enter the respective temple. Larger areas for gathering around found around the platform mounds themselves, with many Cara monumental centers having terraformed areas that are intentionally flattened and tiered around the platform mounds.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Pyramids

Notes: These are large-scale, platform mounds regionally known as pyramids. These house temples.

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: The Cara do not have specific iconography beyond sporadic ritual clay figures that are found, typically abstract and anthropomorph (Echeverría Almeida 1975). There are not consistent representations being made. Interestingly, they do value the importation of goods from surrounding Barbacoan groups, such as the Pasto and the Quijos (Oberem 1974; Hechler 2021). Ceramic corpuses of these groups are more iconographically verbose and are found in Cara ritual spaces, perhaps serving as their own means of filling this local void. Pasto mindalae (traders) often lived amongst the Cara to facilitate interregional exchange - endorsed by the chiefly elite (Salomon 1986).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: This is presumed by the presence of intricate grave goods accompanying elite burials as well as the re-entry into burial mounds by subsequent generations (Oberem & Wurster 1989). There is an interaction with the deceased that suggests continued political participation in society well after their lives, thus it could be implied there is a notion of the afterlife.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Specifically for elites, they would be offered a sumptuary burial in earlier times (-950-1280 CE) -- with exotic ceramic offerings from the Amazon and sometimes even offerings of human crania (Oberem & Wurster 1989)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence of human sacrifices in early burials from 950 CE - 1280 CE, although this practice does not appear to be as common between 1280 CE to Spanish Conquest. Biological anthropological research is still very limited, thus there has not been a concerted effort to understand if these sacrifices are out-group or in-group humans.

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear, as many of the documented human sacrifices were from earlier generations before the advent of modern bioanthropological approaches.

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear, as many of the documented human sacrifices were from earlier generations before the advent of modern bioanthropological approaches.

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear, as many of the documented human sacrifices were from earlier generations before the advent of modern bioanthropological approaches.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear, animal remains have been found in close association with human remains, but it is unclear if these were formal sacrifices or a result of refuse from feasting during mortuary interments. Many of these contexts were found before modern bioanthropological methodologies.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Grave goods are typically ceramic vessels, a mixture of locally made vessels as well as imported ceramics from the Upper Amazon from the nearby Quijos ethnic group.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Body adornments, such as tinkullpas (pectoral pendants), have been found in mortuary contexts (Jijón y Caamaño 1921).

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Perhaps by local standards. There have been some interments of gold funerary masks documented, such as at Huataviro (Pazmiño Tamayo 2014), although typically metal adornments were copper (Jijón y Caamaño 1921).

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Ceramics, local and exotic, shells, worked animal and human bone as flutes (Oberem & Wurster 1989).

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Ceramics, local and exotic, shells, worked animal and human bone as flutes (Oberem & Wurster 1989).

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Exotic ceramics from the Amazon were highly prized in formal interments (Oberem & Wurster 1989; Hechler 2021).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly. Rounded burial mounds (950 CE - 1280 CE) have been excavated with no human remains, although the entire structure is constructed, filled, and offered grave goods as any other burial mound of the region, including have a central chamber that lacks human remains. This may be a potential indicator of a cenotaph.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: While commoners do not appear to have a formally organized cemetery, elites do have organized clusters of rounded burial mounds (950 CE - 1280 CE) that often complement natural landscape features, such as quebradas.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: There is ethnohistoric mention of this but archaeological evidence is limited.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Shallow pit-and-chamber tombs are found around ritual monumental centers.

Notes: There does not appear to be a formal organizational patterning to these, and these are often modest with one individual in a flexed position with minimal to no tomb goods. If artifacts are present, they are typically local ceramics or perhaps a small vessel imported from the Quijos of the Upper Amazon.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The reality of the deities observed prior to the Inka conquest is unclear, however immediately after there is a heavy influence of Catequil - the god of thunder and lightning from Huamachuco of the central highlands of Peru - with the presence of mitmaquna (Topic et al. 2002). This would have likely been culturally intelligible by the Cara who revered water features and acknowledged them through the monumental planning (Haro Alvear 1974; Espinoza Soriano 1988; Hechler et al. 2022; Brown 2023).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While this is unclear, the dead likely played a prominent role in then-contemporary politics as monumental graves were reaccessed (Oberem & Wurste 1989; Doyon 2002).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Potentially, there is evidence of this amongst the early Cara between -950-1280 CE, although we do not see much evidence of this after 1280 CE until the Inka conquest.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Potentially, there is evidence of this amongst the early Cara between -950-1280 CE, although we do not see much evidence of this after 1280 CE until the Inka conquest.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: In some manner, yes, although exactly how this worked prior to the Inka conquest is unclear. Monumental centers served as important ritual pilgrimage modes on the local landscape. Unfortunately, how this functioned is archaeologically and ethnohistorically unclear.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Small-scale rituals clearly took place within private ceremonies on pyramid summits within enclosed temple spaces, although what these rituals exactly were is still unclear as the impact of Inka colonialism erased any serious ethnohistoric mentions of these practices.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is unclear, although monumental centers could potentially house thousands of participants.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably there were seasonal practices that occurred, although if these were one-and-the-same with Inka seasonal observances (Guaman Poma [1615] 1936) is unclear, especially since seasons along the equator in Ecuador are not as distinct as in the central highlands of Peru.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While this has not been proven archaeologically nor ethnohistorically, there is regional precedent amongst related Barbacoan neighbors of the use of intoxicants for ritual purposes.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unfortunately this is unknown during the Cara independence, however after the regional conquest by the Inka Empire, the Inka did introduce qullqas (storage facilities) for storing locally harvested agricultural products for redistribution (Salomon 1986: 170). Stored goods from these could have been implemented during famine at the discretion of the Inka state, although there does not appear to have been historical episodes of famine.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: After the regional conquest by the Inka Empire, the Inka did introduce qullqas (storage facilities) for storing locally harvested agricultural products for redistribution (Salomon 1986: 170). Stored goods from these could have been implemented during famine at the discretion of the Inka state, although there does not appear to have been historical episodes of famine.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Cara society was organized around what could be termed as distinct classes: paramount chiefs, intermediate chiefs, and commoners (Athens 1992; 1997). There was a fourth class reserved for merchants, although many of these appear to be special sponsored statuses for sponsored traders from the neighboring Barbacoan ethnic group of the Pasto (Salomon 1986).

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Pre-Inka systems of poverty relief are not known. The Inka conquest of the Cara brought in state-sponsored systems of redistribution, although this has been viewed as a non-market economy in which goods - which were already sequestered from the colonized group - were redistributed in return for compliance with expected rendered services through the mit'a - a cyclical corvée tax.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Cara homesteads housed extended families within large bohíos, circular wooden structures with thatched roofs. These were multi-generational homes, thus this was a societal expectation instead of a form of religious care.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Cara homesteads housed extended families within large bohíos, circular wooden structures with thatched roofs. These were multi-generational homes, thus this was a societal expectation instead of a form of religious care.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a religio-political bureaucracy that all members of the group are born into. Cara society was organized around what could be termed as distinct classes: paramount chiefs, intermediate chiefs, and commoners (Athens 1992; 1997). Local level political decisions were dictated by intermediate chiefs who answered to a regional paramount chief.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is unclear archaeologically and ethnohistorically, however this was a practice that occurred in the region after the regional conquest by the Inka Empire.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Inka Empire provided food storage via their qullqa system (Hyslop 1984; 1990).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: This is organized at the community level, likely by intermediate chiefs. There was a complex system of raised field agriculture, known as camellones.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: After the regional conquest by the Inka Empire, the Inka did juxtapose some of their own water management approaches, particularly in ritual contexts. At the site of Inka-Caranquí, a complex system of stone canals funnelled hot and cold water to the royal Inka baths.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is unclear at what level road systems were managed prior to the Inka conquest. These clearly existed and were exploited by the Inka conquerors later.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: After the Inka conquest, the Qhapaq Ñan (royal Inka road) was built throughout Cara territory, as were secondary Inka roads. Many veins of this likely exploited local, pre-existing roads (Hyslop 1984; Fresco González 2004).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the pre-Inka reality of taxation systems is unclear, there was clearly a form of labor organized amongst each polity for the creation of monumental sties (Osborn & Athens 1974; Brown 2023).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: After the regional conquest by the Inka Empire, the Inka enforced the mit'a - a cyclical corvée tax (Salomon 1986)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: After the regional conquest by the Inka Empire, mitmaquna (forcibly relocated ethnic enclaves from elsewhere within the empire) were relocated amongst the Cara (Espinoza Soriano 1975), some colonies of which operated as police forces to maintain loyalty to the empire. Cañari from southern Ecuador (Oberem & Hartmann 1976) and Chachapoya from northern Peru (Salomon 1986) were often implemented.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The Inka Empire enforced its own judicial system within the region upon conquest.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

— Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

— Yes

Notes: The Inka Empire executed regional dissidents after rebellion under Emperor Wayna Qhapaq (e.g., Cieza de León [1553] 2005).

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

— Yes

Notes: The Inka Empire deported entire communities from specific chiefdoms throughout the empire from Ecuador to modern Peru and Bolivia (Hechler et al. 2022).

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

— Yes

Notes: The Inka Empire institutional a variety of corporal punishments based upon a wide range of crimes (Guaman Poma de Ayala [1615] 1936).

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

— Yes

Notes: While the exact contexts are not certain, the Inka Empire did seize prominent land plots for royal estates, infrastructure, and religious architecture.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: The Inka Empire had a formal legal code (Guaman Poma de Ayala [1615] 1936).

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The Inka Empire had a formal legal code (Guaman Poma de Ayala [1615] 1936).

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

— Yes

Notes: The Cara polities could call upon fellow chiefdoms to go to war. The only example we know of this is with the Inka Empire (Espinoza Soriano 1988). In general, prior to the Inka presence, the region was largely peaceful (Brown 2023) and heavily relied on interregional trade amongst each other and neighboring ethnic groups (Hechler 2021).

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

— Yes

Notes: Yes, each chiefdom would bring in its members to oppose the opposing force. Once again, the only context we know of this is the regional resistance to the Inka Empire (Salomon 1986; Espinoza Soriano 1988).

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

— No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Notes: Overall, the Cara would rely on drastic moments of political pressure to organize a military. Interregional exchange was highly important (Hechler 2021) and the sponsorship of important mindales (merchants) by individual chiefs was important (Salomon 1986). The Cara maintained generally peaceful regional relations prior to the Inka presence (Brown 2023).

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: After the Inka suppression of a regional rebellion during the coronation of Emperor Wayna Qhapaq, the Cara were forcibly conscripted into the Inka army and were key members of the Inka resistance against the Spanish conquest (Cieza de León [1553] 2005).

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: After the Inka conquest, the Inka Empire maintained a heavily fortified presence to control the local populations. This was not a form of protection but what local populations were subjected to (Brown 2023).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Inka Empire forced their own calendrical system within the region after its conquest (Guaman Poma de Ayala [1615] 1936).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Labor was organized at the local level and complicated irrigation systems were established, such as raised field agriculture -- locally known as camellones (Knapp 1984; Caillavet 2006; Gondard & López 2006).

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Inka Empire did redistribute locally harvested goods they sequestered as a form of reciprocity. We see this with the presence of qullqas in the region (Hyslop 1984).

- ↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
 - Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

General References

- Reference: Cara, Salomon, Frank. *Native Lords of Quito in the Age of the Incas: The Political Economy of North Andean Chiefdoms*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986.
- Reference: Cara, Caillavet, Chantal. *Etnias Del Norte: Etnohistoria E Historia De Ecuador*. Quito: Ediciones Abya-Yala, 2000. https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/abya_yala/244/.
- Reference: Cara, Athens, J. Stephen. *El Proceso Evolutivo En Las Sociedades Complejas Y La Ocupación Del Período Tardío-cara En Los Andes Septentrionales Del Ecuador*. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, 1980. <https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/132242-opac>.
- Reference: Cara, Oberem, Udo. *Cochasquí: Estudios Arqueológicos*. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, 1980. <https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/9918-opac>.
- Reference: Cara, Oberem, Udo, and Wolfgang Wurster. *Excavaciones En Cochasquí, Ecuador, 1964-1965*. Mainz Am Rhein: Verlag Philipp von Zabern, 1989.
- Reference: Cara, Salomon, Frank. *Los Señores Étnicos De Quito En La Época De Los Incas*. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, n.d. <https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/9877-opac>.
- Reference: Cara, Echeverría Almeida, José. *Las Sociedades Prehispánicas De La Sierra Norte Del Ecuador: Una Aproximación Arqueológica Y Antropológica*. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, 2004.
- Reference: Cara, Brown, David. "Paz Y Guerra En La Sierra Norte Del Ecuador: Las Poderosas Culturas De La Integración Tardía". *Boletín De La Academia Nacional De Historia* 101, no. 209 (2023): 77-127. <https://academiahistoria.org.ec/index.php/boletinesANHE/article/view/364>.
- Reference: Cara, Cordero Ramos, María Auxiliadora. *El Cacicazgo Cayambi: Trayectoria Hacia La Complejidad Social En Los Andes Septentrionales*. Quito: Editorial Abya-Yala, 2009. https://www.academia.edu/900042/El_cacicazgo_Cayambi_Trayectoria_hacia_la_complejidad_social_en_los_Andes_septentrionales_Editorial_Abya.
- Reference: Cara, Athens, J. Stephen. "Etnicidad Y Adaptación: El Período Tardío De La Ocupación Cara En La Sierra Norte Del Ecuador". *Sarance* 24 (1997): 161-204. <https://repositorio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/handle/10469/5745>.
- Reference: Cara, Meyers, Albert. *Los Incas En El Ecuador: Análisis De Los Restos Materiales*. Quito: Ediciones Abya-Yala, 1998. https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/abya_yala/476/.
- Reference: Cara, Meyers, Albert. "Toward a Reconceptualization of the Late Horizon and the Inka Period: Perspectives from Cochasquí, Ecuador and Samaipata, Bolivia". In *Variations in the Expression of Inka Power*, 223-54. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2007. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280917862_Toward_a_Reconceptualization_of_the_Late_Horizon_and_the_Inka_Period_Perspectives_from
- Reference: Cara, Bray, Tamara, and José Echeverría Almeida. "Al Final Del Imperio: El Sitio Arqueológico Inca-caranqui En La Sierra Septentrional Del Ecuador". *Antropología: Cuadernos De Investigación* 13 (2014): 127-50. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26807/ant.v0i13.61>.
- Reference: Cara, Espinoza Soriano, Waldemar. *Los Cayambes Y Carangues: Siglos XV-XVI, El Testimonio De La Etnohistoria*. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, 1988. <https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/143177-opac>.
- Reference: Cara, Hechler, Ryan Scott. "Over the Andes, and Through Their Goods: Late Pre-columbian Political Economic Relations in Northern Ecuador". In *The Archaeology of the Upper Amazon: Complexity and Interaction in the Andean Tropical Forest*, 208-27. Gainesville: University Press of Florida, 2021. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1xcxqz3.15>.
- Reference: Cara, Jijón y Caamaño, Jacinto. *Contribución Al Conocimiento De Los Aborígenes De La Provincia De Imbabura En La República Del Ecuador*. Madrid: Blass y Cía, 1914.
- Reference: Cara, Jijón y Caamaño, Jacinto. *Nueva Contribución Al Conocimiento De Los Aborígenes De La Provincia De Imbabura De La República Del Ecuador*. Quito: Tipografía y Encuadernación Salesianas, 1920.
- Reference: Cara, Jijón y Caamaño, Jacinto. *El Ecuador Interandino Y Occidental Antes De La Conquista Castellana*. Quito: Editorial Ecuatoriana, 1940. <https://repositorio.bne.gob.ec/xmlui/handle/34000/1056>.
- Reference: Cara, Uhle, Max. "Die Ruinen Von Cochasquí (nördlich Von Quito)". *Ibero-amerikanisches Archiv* 7, no. 2 (1934): 127-34. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43135768>.
- Reference: Cara, Grijalva, Carlos Emilio. *La Expedición De Max Uhle a Cuasmal O Sea La Protohistoria De Imbabura Y Carchi*. Editorial Chimborazo: Quito, 1942.
- Reference: Cara, Murra, John. "The Historic Tribes of Ecuador". In *Handbook of South American Indians*, 2:785-821. Washington, D.C.: Bureau of American Ethnology, 1946.
- Reference: Cara, Uhle, Max. *Estudio Sobre Las Civilizaciones Del Carchi E Imbabura*. Quito: Talleres Tipográficos Nacionales, 1935.
- Reference: Cara, Hechler, Ryan Scott, and Will Pratt. "Cochasquí, 1532 a 1932: 400 Años De Resiliencia Histórica". *Boletín De La Academia Nacional De Historia* 100, no. 208-A (2022): 179-214. <https://academiahistoria.org.ec/index.php/boletinesANHE/article/view/302>.

- Reference: Cara, Athens, J. Stephen. Inventory of Earthen Mound Sites, Northern Highland Ecuador. Quito: Instituto Nacional de Patrimonio Cultural, 2003.
- Reference: Cara, Currie, Elizabeth J. "Archaeological Investigations in the Northern Highlands of Ecuador at Hacienda Zuleta". *Antiquity* 74, no. 284 (2000): 273-74. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00059214>.
- Reference: Cara, Moncayo Echeverría, Patricio. "Un Complejo De Tolas En Atuntaqui-imbabura En La Sierra Norte Del Ecuador". In *Memorias De Las VII Jornadas Internacionales De Historia Social*, 154-66. Quito: Sociedad Amigos de la Genealogía, 1989.
- Reference: Cara, Gondard, Pierre, and Freddy López. *Inventario Arqueológico Preliminar De Los Andes Septentrionales Del Ecuador*. Quito: Banco Central del Ecuador, 1983. <https://www.documentation.ird.fr/hor/fdi:17855>.
- Reference: Cara, Juan, Jorge, and Antonio de Ulloa. *Relacion Historica Del Viage a La America Meridional : Hecho De Orden De S. Mag. Para Medir Algunos Grados De Meridiano Terrestre, Y Venir Por Ellos En Conocimiento De La Verdadera Figura, Y Magnitud De La Tierra, Con Otras Varias Observaciones Astronomicas, Y Phisicas : Primera Parte. Vol. 2*. Madrid: Antonio Marin, 1748. <https://cb.lunaimaging.com/luna/servlet/detail/JCB-3-3-25695-115904766:Relacion-historica-del-viage-a-la-A>.
- Reference: Cara, Guaman Poma de Ayala, Felipe. *Nueva Corónica Y Buen Gobierno (codex Péruvien Illustré)*. Paris: Institut d'ethnologie, 1936. <https://bvpb.mcu.es/iberoamerica/es/consulta/registro.do?control=BVPBB20170009771>.
- Reference: Cara, Jijón y Caamaño, Jacinto. "Los Tincullpas Y Notas Acerca De La Metalurgia De Los Aborígenes Del Ecuador". *Boletín De La Academia Nacional De Historia* 1, no. 1 (1921): 4-43.
- Reference: Cara, Athens, J. Stephen. "Ethnicity and Adaptation: The Late Period-cara Occupation in Northern Highland Ecuador". In *Resources, Power, and Interregional Interaction*, edited by Edward Schortman and Patricia Urban, 193-219. New York: Plenum Press, 1992.
- Reference: Cara, Haro Alvear, Silvio Luis. *El Culto Del Agua En El Reino De Quito*. Quito: Imprenta La Favorita, 1974.
- Reference: Cara, Topic, John, Theresa Topic, and Alfredo Melly Cava. "Catequil: The Archaeology, Ethnohistory and Ethnography of a Major Provincial Huaca". In *Andean Archaeology I: Variations in Sociopolitical Organization*, edited by William Isbell and Helaine Silverman, 303-36. New York: Kluwer Academic & Plenum Publishers, 2002. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-0639-3_11.
- Reference: Cara, Jijón y Caamaño, Jacinto. *Antropología Prehispánica Del Ecuador*. Quito: La Prensa Católica, 1951.
- Reference: Cara, Osborn, Alan, and J. Stephen Athens. "Prehistoric Earth Mounds in the Highlands of Ecuador: A Preliminary Report". In *Archaeological Investigations in the Highlands of Northern Ecuador: Two Preliminary Reports*, edited by J. Stephen Athens and Alan Osborn, 1-25. Otavalo, Ecuador: Instituto Otavaleño de Antropología, 1974.
- Reference: Cara, Willingham, Eileen. "Imagining the Kingdom of Quito: Reading History and National Identity in Juan De Velasco's *Historia Del Reino De Quito*". In *Jesuit Accounts of the Colonial Americas: Intellectual Transfers, Intellectual Disputes, and Textualities*, edited by Marc Bernier, Clorinda Donato, and Hans-Jürgen Lüsbrink, 81-106. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781442663480-005>.
- Reference: Cara, de Velasco, Juan. *Historia Del Reino De Quito En La América Meridional*. Edited by Agustín Yerovi. Quito: Imprenta del Gobierno, 1844. <https://archive.org/details/52451836HistoriaDelReinoDeQuitoEnLaAmericaMeridionalVol1>.
- Reference: Cara, de Cieza de León, Pedro. *Crónica Del Perú: El Señorío De Los Incas*. Edited by Franklin Pease C.Y.. Caracas: Biblioteca Ayacucho, 2005.
- Reference: Cara, Cabello Balboa, Miguel. *Miscelánea Antártica : Una Historia Del Perú Antiguo*. Lima: Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos, Instituto de Etnología y Arqueología, 1951.
- Reference: Cara, Garcilaso de la Vega, Inca. *Comentarios Reales De Los Incas*. Edited by Aurelio Miró Quesada. Caracas: Biblioteca Ayacucho, 1976.
- Reference: Cara, Diez de Betanzos, Juan. *Suma Y Narración De Los Incas*. Edited by María del Carmen Martín Rubio. Madrid: Polifemo, 2004.
- Reference: Cara, Oberem, Udo. "Trade and Trade Goods in the Ecuadorian Montaña". In *Native South Americans: Ethnology of the Least Known Continent*, edited by Patricia Lyon, 346-57. Boston: Little, Brown and Company, 1974.
- Reference: Cara, Knapp, Gregory. *Soil, Slope and Water in the Equatorial Andes: A Study of Prehistoric Agricultural Adaptation*. Madison: University of Wisconsin-Madison, 1984. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280733787_Soil_Slope_and_Water_in_the_Equatorial_Andes_A_Study_of_Prehistoric_Agricultural_Adapta
- Reference: Cara, Gondard, Pierre, and Freddy López. "Albarradas Y Camellones: Drenaje, Riego Y Heladas En Cayambe (sierra Norte Del Ecuador)". In *Agricultura Ancestral Camellones Y Albarradas*, edited by Francisco Valdez, 241-50. Quito: Abya-Yala, 2006.
- Reference: Cara, Caillavet, Chantal. "Historia Y Agricultura Autóctona En Los Andes Ecuatorianos: El Complejo Campos Elevados, En Ecosistemas Diversos (siglos XV-XVII)". In *Agricultura Ancestral Camellones Y Albarradas*, edited by Francisco Valdez, 111-26. Quito: Abya-Yala, 2006.
- Reference: Cara, Hyslop, John. *The Inka Road System*. Orlando: Academic Press, 1984.
- Reference: Cara, Fresco González, Antonio. *Ingañán: La Red Vial Del Imperio Inca En Los Andes*

Ecuatoriales. Quito: Banco Central del Ecuador, 2004.

Reference: Cara, Espinoza Soriano, Waldemar. "Los Mitmas Huayacuntu En Quito O Guarniciones Para La Represión Armada, Siglos XV Y XVI". *Revista Del Museo Nacional* 41 (1975): 351-94.

Reference: Cara, Oberem, Udo, and Roswith Hartmann. "Indios Cañaris De La Sierra Sur Del Ecuador En El Cuzco Del Siglo XVI". *Revista De La Universidad Complutense: Economía Y Sociedad En Los Andes Y Mesoamérica* 28, no. 117 (n.d.): 373-90.

Reference: Cara, Hyslop, John. *Inka Settlement Planning*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1990.

Reference: Cara, Pazmiño Tamayo, Estanislao. "Huataviro Y Los Señoríos De La Sierra Norte Del Ecuador".

INPC: *Revista Del Patrimonio Cultural Del Ecuador* 5 (2014): 56-69.

<https://revistas.patrimoniocultural.gob.ec/ojs/index.php/INPC/issue/view/8>.

Reference: Cara, Doyon, Leon. "Conduits of Ancestry: Interpretation of the Geography, Geology, and Seasonality of North Andean Shaft Tombs". *Archeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association* 11, no. 1 (2002): 79-95. <https://doi.org/10.1525/ap3a.2002.11.1.79>.